

Studies and Synthesis of Coumarinyl-*s*-triazine Derivatives as Potential Antibacterial Agents

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Coumarins¹, phenoxyethers of *s*-triazines², 2,4-dichloro-6-triazinylthioureas³ and thioureas⁴ possess various biological activities.

In continuation of our previous efforts to prepare potential antibacterial agents, we have synthesised 2-(4'-methylcoumarin-7'-yloxy)-4-(4'-acetanidoanil-no)-6-(arylthioureido)-*s*-triazines (3).

4-Methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin was prepared from resorcinol and ethylacetoacetate. Cyanuric chloride and 4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin were reacted to give the intermediate 1. It was further treated with *p*-acetamidoaniline to give the intermediate 2, which on condensation with various arylthioureas gave corresponding *s*-triazine derivatives (3) (Scheme 1).

Experimental

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 599 B spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian EM 390 spectrophotometer. Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds were checked by tlc using acetone + ethyl acetate + petroleum ether + water (100 : 100 : 3 : 3.5) solvent system.

4-Methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin⁵ and various arylthioureas⁶ were prepared by the following reported methods.

2-(4'-Methylcoumarin-7'-yloxy)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine (1)⁷: A solution of 4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (1.76 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone was added dropwise

Scheme 1

with stirring to a solution of cyanuric chloride (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone in an ice-bath (0–5°). The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at 0–5° and neutral pH was maintained by adding aqueous NaHCO₃. It was then poured onto crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol (80%), m.p. 235°.

*2-(4'-Methylcoumarin-7'-yloxy)-4-(4'-acetamidoanilino)-6-chloro-s-triazine (2)*⁷: *p*-Acetamidoaniline (1.5 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in minimum quantity of acetone, was added slowly with stirring over a period of 0.5 h to a solution of **1** (3.34 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 35°. The reaction mixture was stirred further for 2 h, during which period temperature was gradually raised to 45° and neutral pH was maintained by adding aqueous NaHCO₃. It was then poured onto crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol (72%), m.p. 196°.

*2-(4'-Methylcoumarin-7'-yloxy)-4-(4'-acetamidoanilino)-6-(arythioureido)-s-triazine (3)*⁷. *General method*: A mixture of **2** (4.37 g, 0.01 mol) and arylthiourea (0.01 mol) in acetone (100 ml) was refluxed for 3 h on a water-bath. Aqueous NaHCO₃ was occasionally added to maintain neutral pH. It was then cooled to the room temperature and poured onto crushed ice. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol (Table 1); ν_{\max} 795–810 (*s*-triazine ring), 1 260 (C–O–C), 1 700 (C=O – lactones), 3 300 – 3 310 (2° amine) and 1 485 cm⁻¹ 1 500 cm⁻¹ (C–N substituted thioureas); **3d** δ 6.67 (NH thiourea), 7.4–8.4 (ArH), 2.3 (CH₃), 1.8 (NHCOCH₃) and 10.1 (NH–Ar); **3g** δ 6.69 (NH thiourea), 7.4–8.4 (ArH), 2.31 (CH₃), 1.8 (NHCOCH₃), 7.15 (ClC₆H₄) and 10.12 (NH–Ar); **3i** δ 6.69 (NH thiourea), 7.4–8.3 (ArH), 2.31 (CH₃), 1.81 (NHCOCH₃) and 10.12 (NH–Ar).

Antibacterial activity: Compounds **3** were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *P. vulgaris* and *S. paratyphi B.*, following agar-diffusion method⁸. A standard

sterilised filter paper disc (5 mm dia) impregnated with the solution of compound in acetone (1 mg ml⁻¹) was placed on an agar plate seeded with the test organism. The plates were incubated for 24 h at 37° and the zone of inhibition of bacterial growth around the disc was observed. The zone of inhibition data of all the compounds (**3a–j**) against all the organisms were found in the range 0.0–2.5 mm against standard drugs ampicillin (5.0 mm against *S. aureus*), erythromycin (6.0 mm, *B. subtilis*), gentamycin (6.0 mm, *E. coli*), penicillin (6.0 mm, *P. vulgaris*) and chloramphenicol (6.0 mm, *S. paratyphi B.*). No significant result was obtained as compared to the standard drugs. Hence, no specific structure activity relationship could be established. However chloro substitution in thioureidophenyl ring culminated in compounds with better activity.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **3***

Compd no	R	M p °C	R _f
3a	C ₆ H ₅	157	0.79
b	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	166	0.83
c	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	201	0.81
d	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	174	0.89
e	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	179	0.65
f	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	175	0.78
g	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	156	0.89
h	<i>o</i> -O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	151	0.71
i	<i>m</i> -O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	147	0.69
j	<i>p</i> -O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	184	0.75

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis for C, H, N and S, yields 57–69%

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NOTE

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